

THRIVE – Advisory Group

Maribel Labrid
Head of Human Resources
& Academic Affairs

Margarida Corminas
Managing Director

Cristina Horcajada
Head of Innovation

Jorge Domínguez
Scientific Management
Coordinator

Anna Montras
Head of Competitive Funding &
International Promotion

Suresh Raman
Section Head of International
Promotion

